

Project **ROOTS & SFB1266 Landman**
Application **LandMan-Repository (LM24-Repo)**
State of Template **29.09.2024**

Explanation of data elements in Repository. The completion of your documentation will be done in a meeting with LM-Coordination.

Label	Entry	Description	Value
Database-ID	SYS	Unique identifier of data record	<automatically set by system>
Content Information:			
Title	REQ	Title of data collection	
Author(s)	REQ	Authors of data collection; Format: FirstName1 LastName1; FirstName2 LastName2; ... <u>authors separated by semicolon.</u>	
Contributors	OPT	Persons & organisations which additionally to authors contributed for data collection multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon	
Abstract	OPT	Short description of the research project / research question and the resulting data collection (max. 300 words). In contrast to the detailed description, the abstract serves primarily for quick recording, e.g. in overviews or list presentations.	
Description	OPT	Detailed description of the (research) project and the resulting data collection. The information about the scientific context in which the data were generated may be important to gain an understanding of the quality and quantity of the data. The information about the data collection may refer to structure, collection issues or other relevant infos for further usage.	
Keywords	REQ	Useful keywords for data collection; separated by semicolon. Please use at least one or several of the given terms (see "Values" tab) for keywords. You may add as many other terms as you need here on top.	
Sources	OPT	Sources used for creating data collection; multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon	
Language(s)	OPT	Language(s) of data collection; according to ISO 639-2 multiple entries separated by semicolon	

Publication(s)	OPT	Publications based on data collection multiple entries possible	
Collection Type	REQ	Classification of data collection type; actual list of values: Research Data / External Data Base / Code Base / Other;	
Format	OPT	Format of data collection; example values: .xlsx, .docx, .mdb, .accdb, .pdf, .csv, .txt, online database et al. multiple entries separated by semicolon	
Extent	OPT	Extent of data collection; size of data collection in MB/GB multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon	
DNB DDC	OPT	Dewey Decimal Classification of Deutsche National Bibliothek (930 for Archaeology) (see "Values" tab); multiple entries separated by semicolon	
Additional Info	OPT	Any additional information for data collection	
Spatio-Temporal Categorization:			
Period(s)	REQ	Period(s) (e.g. archaeological) of data collection; multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon. Stick to the given terms (see "Values" tab), for any other terms use "Period(s) addition" below.	
Period(s) Addition	OPT	Additional infos for period(s) (e.g. archaeological) of data collection e.g. to describe not categorized sub- periods or any other relevant infos; multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon	
Other Classification	OPT	Arbitrary classification of data collection, e.g. for botanical or geological categories; multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon.	
Content Dating Start	REQ	Described findings or objects from time range starting with this year; Format: BCE/CE, e.g.: 2800 BCE	
Content Dating End	REQ	Described findings or objects from time range ending with this year; Format: BCE/CE, e.g.: 500 CE	

Region(s)	REQ	Geographical region(s) of findings or objects documented in data collection; multiple entries possible, separated by semicolon; preferably values according to ISO 3166-1/3 & ISO 3166-2; please enter full country names in English here.	
Region(s) Addition	OPT	Any additional infos for region of data collection, e.g. sub- or supraregional constructs. Multiple entries separated by semicolon. E.g.: Scandinavia; Northern Germany; Duvensee	
Marker Position(s)	OPT	Values for position of marker(s) on LandMan Map Format: Decimal Coordinates (Latitude, Longitude) (WGS 84) separated by comma, multiple entries separated by semicolon, e.g.: 15.127, 27.410; Latitude2, Longitude2; ...	
Coverage	SYS	Coverage of data collection; virtuell field for use in display & lists; showing preceding 6 fields concatenated	<automatically set by system>
Data Collection Process:			
Project Reference(s)	OPT	Project(s) in which the data was collected; multiple entries separated by semicolon; please add subproject(s) involved	
Created start	OPT	Year of data collection start	
Created end	REQ	Year of data collection end	
Last modified	REQ	Date of last modification of data collection, format: dd.mm.yyyy	
Published	SYS	Date of publishing meta data for open access in this repository	<set by LM-Coordination>
Meta Data Responsibility & Sharing			
Metadata Owner	REQ	Organisation or person with ownership and responsibility of the metadata of the data collection in the LM-Repository as described in this document.	
MD Owner Username	SYS	Username of Metadata Owner to sign in for LandMan-Repository	<set by LM-Coordination>
Metadata Contact	REQ	Person (Name; Email Address) named by metadata owner to be responsible for delivering & maintaining the metadata contents in repository; contact point of LM-Coordination for all tasks & questions concerning content of the meta data & data collection.	
MD Contact Username	SYS	Username of Metadata Contact to sign in for LandMan-Repository	<set by LM-Coordination>
Citation	OPT	Citation for data collection, e.g.: Authors; Year of publication; Title; Repository name; DOI; <opt: status, e.g. dataset in review>	

DOI	OPT	DOI (Digital Object Identifier) if existing; multiple entries separated by semicolon	
Access to Dataset	REQ	Infos to access data collection; URL for direct data access or contact info for requesting access to data; also used for documentation of versions of the data set(s).	
License	OPT	Specification of license for data collection (see "Values" tab). Mandatory if data is public.	
Meta Data Administration			
Mergeable	REQ	Flag (True or False) for indication availability for data merge operations (esp. in LandMan)	FALSE
Private	REQ	Flag (True or False) for indication of restricted access only for metadata owner, metadata contact & authorized users	TRUE
Disabled	SYS	Flag (True or False) to mark deactivated records (e.g. which are requested to be deleted); records with this flag = TRUE not shown in searches, listings & displays	<set by LM-Coordination>
Submitter	SYS	Username of submitter of data record	<automatically set by system>
Submit Date	SYS	Timestamp of data record creation	<automatically set by system>
Last Modified by	SYS	Username of user who did last modification of data record	<automatically set by system>
Last Modified Date	SYS	Timestamp of last modification of data record	<automatically set by system>